

In Colombia's fields, small farms take flight,
El Niño and La Niña, nature's delicate might.
Coffee's dance with warmth, a surprising song,
La Niña's rain, in rhythm, along.

Figures whisper, correlations unfold,
ONI and SPI, a story told.
In the CESM's gaze, the future unfurls,
A climatic waltz, in changing swirls.

El Niño, once foe, now a coffee's friend,
La Niña's embrace, droughts amend.
Yet, in recent years, a shift in the air,
El Niño's rise, a tale to bear.

In this agro-poetic refrain, lessons unfurl,
A dance with nature, a resilient swirl.